

IDENTITY CRISIS IN LEWIS CARROLL'S "ALICE THROUGH THE LOOKING GLASS"

Andreas Tano ¹,
Gustaman Saragih ²,

English Language Education, Postgraduate Program, Universitas Indraprasta PGRI

e-mail: andreas.tano@yahoo.com ¹

e-mail: gustaman.saragih@unindra.ac.id ²

Abstract: This research aims at showing the connection between the characters' reality and fantasy on identity crisis in *Alice through the Looking-Glass* novel by Lewis Carroll. Thus, the conducted research was analyzed using qualitative method with the approach of psychoanalytical literary criticism: *Psychoanalysis* by Freud as well as the theory of *Psychosocial Development* by Erikson to seek the identity crisis of the character Alice. As the conclusion of the research, **1)** Alice's 'ego' cannot manage her 'id' which is difficult to be gratified in reality that triggers Alice overreact her defense mechanisms. **2)** Alice's fantasy works as a defense mechanism which is caused by her unfulfilled wishes. **3)** It is revealed that Alice experiences identity crisis at the phase of autonomy versus doubt and shame as well as initiative versus guilt which influences her behaviors, resulting *Childhood Onset schizophrenic (COS)* personality disorder.

Keywords: Identity Crisis, Psychoanalysis; Interpretation of Dreams; Personality Disorder; Schizophrenia.

Introduction

Alice through the looking glass is one of the most famous classic literary works which is presented in a type of an illustrated novel consisting a narrative and pictures that enables the readers not limited to reading, but also creating images while enjoying the story in the reader's mind. This illustrated novel was published in 2015 by Templar Publishing; an imprint of The Templar Company Limited, U.K. The writer of the novel also gives credit to the illustrator, Robert Ingpen and the layout that was designed by Palazzo Editions, Ltd. The novel contains remarkable illustrations by Ing Pen that won an award for portraying Alice and her second adventure in exquisite detail and using a variety of media including pencil, pastel, and watercolor.

Alice is a child who spends most of her time playing with her cat and her fantasy to seek pleasure from her play. *Alice, through the looking glass*, is the next sequel of the previous story; *Alice in wonderland*. Though both narratives are considered as the works of children's literature, they implicitly reflect on the issue of the development of a child. The main character, in *Alice through the looking glass*, who is in the phase of early teenager is portrayed in a narrative using a child's point of view; in which the problem she is fantasizing more associated with maturity. In the first chapter, Alice talks to her kitten and invites her to play a pretend game to be a red queen. However, she realizes that a kitten cannot act and talk like a human. Suddenly, she enters into a looking glasshouse where everything is reversed and begun. This indicates the existence of the implication of her psychological disturbance; in addition, it implicitly tells that she cannot help herself to wish as if she were mature as a queen in her fantasy. The crucial issue of this sequel lies in her psychological problem when she is unable to manage her anxiety regarding social life.

Through this novel, some elements of literature such as the characters, the plot, as well as the illustrations including pictures, symbols and colors will be discussed by using a psychological approach of literary criticism: psychoanalysis. The theory of reality principle, as well as the interpretation of dreams by Sigmund Freud, is and the related theory of psychosocial by Erik H. Erikson are occupied with supporting the analysis of the research. Psychoanalytic criticism is "a form of literary criticism which uses some of the techniques of psychoanalysis in the interpretation of literature" (Barry, 1995: 96). Psychoanalytical literary criticism is an approach used to interpret significant sentences and direct speeches regarding the psychological issue of

characters in a narrative to reveal a particular personality disorder that is suffered by the main character. Furthermore, the contrast between reality and fantasy aspects that influence the behaviors toward Alice’s identity crisis will be analyzed and compared by using binary opposition: the reality versus the fantasy. Thus, this research, entitled: “The Characters’ Reality and Fantasy on Identity Crisis in Lewis Carroll’s Alice Through the Looking Glass.”

This research focuses on the reality and fantasy aspects of the characters which are in the scope of literature. Psychoanalysis was used as a literary approach in conducting the research. Furthermore, the researcher analyzed how the reality in Alice through the looking glass novel affects Alice’s identity crisis and how the fantasy in Alice through the looking glass novel portrays personality disorder issue. The result of the research was expected to discover the connection between the characters’ reality and fantasy or dream in Alice through the looking glass towards her identity crisis. In addition, how the character manages her identity crisis was also discussed.

Conducting this research: binary opposition was used to compare and contrast the distinction between reality and the fantasy of the characters. Binary opposition is a prevalent instrument used for literary analysis. It is divided into two contrast characteristics: the opposites. The reality towards the ‘ego’ of the character that represents the normality; meanwhile, the fantasy is one of the defense mechanisms represents the abnormality. Hence, here was the instrument occupied:

Table 1
Binary Opposition

Reality	Fantasy
“ Reality is a particular form of existence not to be focused on material reality, in relation to the unconscious and conscious mental processes.” (Ekins, 2002:9-10)	“ Fantasy is a certain amount of dream/daydream that can be quite positive – it is harmful when a person no longer separate fantasy from reality.” (Rose, 2011:136)
“ Reality is attributed to something which ‘really’ exists or real intuitively outside the mind and is independent of its being perceived.” (Oliner, 2012:60)	“ Fantasies are daydreams and contends that they, like dreams, are without exception wish-fulfillment.” (Freud in Adams, 2014:5)
“ Reality refers to something subjective, something felt or sensed, rather than to an external realm of being existing independently of the human subject.” (Rose, 2011:60)	“ Fantasies are real psychic entities that stay in touch with the unconscious, and they can enter the conscious; images that flow when we are asleep.” Jung in (Snowden, 2017:175)

Based on the above instrument, the aspects of reality and fantasy were compared and contrasted in order to figure out the personality disorder of the character as well as the effect of the defense mechanism towards the identity crisis. All the sentences or direct speeches from the novel related to the two aspects were then analyzed in order to get the result of the research.

Method

This research study used the Qualitative approach to collect, analyze, and describe the data taken from the object. Dawson (2002:14) stated that qualitative research explores attitudes, behavior, and experiences. It means that the research that requires a researcher to describe or explain the attitude, behavior, and experiences can use a qualitative approach. Furthermore, Kothary (2004: 3) stated that:

Qualitative research is especially important in the behavioral sciences, where the aim is to discover the underlying motives of human behavior. Through such research, we can analyze the various factors which motivate people to behave in a particular manner or which make people like or dislike a particular thing.

Cothary’s statement explains that a qualitative approach can be used to analyze the various motives of human behaviors. Since the object of the research was novel, in the scope of literature using psychoanalytical criticism,

qualitative approach fitted to analyze the behaviors and motives of the characters. Qualitative research enables a researcher to reveal various factors which motivate people to behave in particular manners. In addition, it can influence the readers to create an opinion towards the result of the research. Therefore, this research was conducted using the qualitative approach with the activities like reading the novel many times, selecting significant sentences, identifying, analyzing the data, getting the findings, and drawing the conclusion.

Results and Discussion

In the picture, Alice is floating in the air and getting into a mirror, giving a sense of her pre-conscious phase. A face of a queen is pictured with the box and a pawn beside it; gives the correlation with the character in the looking-glass world she is entering. The illustration of Alice is being sucked into the mirror shows that Alice is entering the subconscious as the manifestation of her pre-conscious fantasy.

“So I shall be as warm here as I was in the old room,” thought Alice, “warmer, in fact, because there’ll be no one here to scold me away from the fire. Oh, what fun it’ll be, when they see me through the glass in here, and can’t get at me!” (Carroll, p.19). The warm in the old room can be meant as the warmth with her mother in her past. She is very excited about being in the glass because no one can scold and get at her. It means that she tries to escape from her reality by having a fantasy like this, and she thinks it is fun to be there.

Figure 1. Alice enters the room

In the glass, she can have the freedom to have all she wishes that of her ‘id’ requires to be pleased. Furthermore, it is fun if no one can keep her from what she wants. She sees her old room that symbolizes her past as something that is unpleasant; however, her ‘id’ demands something different from her reality. Her past could be something that is unpleasant related to a problem in her family: like the relationship between a mother and a child. The more she gets into her fantasy, the more it becomes wild beyond her control or her ‘ego.’

“Are you a child or a teetotum?” the Sheep said, as she took up another pair of needles” (Carroll, p.93). At this time, her ‘super-ego’ questions her back regarding her age, whether she is a child or a teetotum. A teetotum is the symbol of something repeating over and over, but it is stuck in one place. It gives an idea that as a seven and a half-year-old child, she cannot decide what she wants to do, but rather than the role of parents more dominant. Moreover, the sharp point and the hole of needles are the symbols of parents. It means that whatever she does, rules are needed to be obeyed. In the previous analysis, she needs her parents’ guidance in order to be tidy and orderly.

Figure 2. Alice and Humpty Dumpty

The given illustration is shown from above and from one side; it is meant to focus the viewers on the character Alice below Humpty Dumpty. The close distance: one hand is holding the other’s shows the intimate

interaction between the two of them. The little Alice looks helping the big Humpty Dumpty get off from the wall; it helps the viewers know the courage of the character Alice even though she is helping him using one of the small bricks. *“Humpty Dumpty was sitting, with his legs crossed like a Turk, on the top of a high wall – such a narrow one that Alice quite wondered how he could keep his balance.”* (Carroll, p.102). Humpty Dumpty is a disrespectful egg-like man based on the nursery rhyme character who likes to sit on a wall and treats Alice rudely. He is the one who tells the meaning of “Jabberwocky” to Alice but changes the meanings of words. The egg is the symbol of her mother who is a role model for a child to develop her infantile super-ego though norms and morals; nevertheless, it represents her ‘id’ in this part because one of the characteristics of ‘id’ is to seek ways to gratify its drive. The wall symbolizes a significant obstacle in Alice’s life that she must go through to achieve what she wants. The height represents the big circumstances that she is going through. On this account, the high wall is a depiction of rules or her mother’s high expectation towards Alice. While wondering how he balances himself on the wall, Alice’s ‘ego’ questions herself how she is able to get through her obstacle, such as rules at home and tidiness that she cannot organize. In this context, her ‘id’ tries various ways to be gratified by her ‘ego’. *“It’s a cravat, child, and a beautiful one, as you say. It’s a present from the White King and Queen. There now!”* (Carroll, p.106). A cravat is worn around a person’s neck; therefore, it represents a sense of restriction where responsibility is concerned. Freud (2008:123) stated that “A tie or cravat for the male organ, or wood for the female one.” On this account, a cravat is a gift of morals, norms, and rules that are passed on by her parents that are needed to be obeyed.

Based on the description of the reality and the fantasy regarding the relationship with Alice’s mother, it is concluded that during Alice’s age, she wants to be like her mother as a role model of herself both in reality and fantasy. Erikson (1993:249) stated that “Parents must not only have certain ways of guiding by prohibition and permission; they must also be able to represent to the child a deep, an almost somatic conviction that there is a meaning to what they are doing.” In other words, apart from prohibiting or permitting a child of doing something, parents should be able to be a role model for their child. Alice has some obstacles to manage her tidiness. It has something to do with her past unpleasant experience regarding her potty training. Besides, she needs support from her parents; on this account, it is the warmth of her mother that she does not have it anymore. Hence, Alice’s age is the period when she is having difficulty to manage herself without the guidance of a parent in order to assume responsibility well. In her fantasy, it is indicated that she is having a judgment of being a dependent girl from her closest persons, especially in her family. It has a correlation with the strict rules in her home that she is unable to follow completely. Erikson in Syed (2017:4) stated that:

“In early childhood, children learn to take greater risks in separating from their caregiver, actively engaging with their environments on their own terms—taking the initiative. The negative pole, guilt, corresponds to the guilt associated with engaging in work that is not intricately tied to the caregiver—that initiating independent play serves as a betrayal of the established bond.”

During this period, a child has many initiatives in doing like an adult. The curiosity often causes a child undertakes many adult-like activities, sometimes overstepping the limits set by parents. The role of a mother; thus, is vital during the phase of ‘Initiative; Guilty.’ Over judgment from a parent may result a child has guilty feeling. As a result, the gap relationship between a parent and a child makes a child seek escapement from reality by having fantasy play or projecting her anxiety to a particular object. In this context, a mother is the first role model of a child whose parenting is the key to the succession of initiative in the future. The limitation of initiative feeling by blaming a child who makes a mistake will result in having lack of self-confidence or afraid of wrongdoing. As a shred of evidence, Alice prefers playing with her fantasy or with her cat as an escape of her reality. Therefore, in reality, she is easily mad with her cat when something is untidy. She does this as a defense mechanism to relieve her anxiety towards her inability to manage her tidiness. Giving an opportunity to explore her initiative doing makes a child gain experience, independence, and self-confidence.

This illustration shows that Alice is holding her cat and a piece of wool thread is curled up around the kitten’s neck. It shows that Alice is a playful kid who loves to play with her cat while doing another activity. The close-up picture is shown to show the personality of the character, which is not carefully winding the

worsted ball with her cat. It also shows the close relationship between Alice and her cat whether it is a friend to play with or just a pet cat.

Figure 3. The Playful Alice

“While Alice was sitting curled up in the corner of the great armchair, half talking to herself and half asleep, the kitten had been having a grand game of romps with the ball of worsted Alice had been trying to wind up....” (Carroll, p.14).

It is evident that she loves tidiness that she is angry with her cat and cannot manage herself to control her emotion in reality because it loves to play with the worsted ball. At this point, she is half asleep, giving the idea that she is pre-conscious after having a long talk to her cat. In order to figure out what she wishes in reality, it requires in-depth analysis of her unconscious; of which Freud in Snowden (2017:70) stated that “all the hidden wishes, in reality, play the biggest part in reality and may appear in the unconscious; either in manifested or latent fantasies in dreams.” Alice is a girl who loves something orderly and tidy; nonetheless, she is quite moody, and she often gets mad whenever her cats make a mess. On this account, her behavior is influenced by her pre-conscious that makes her behave such way. Furthermore, the reality principle clarifies how ‘ego’ manages the gratification of ‘id’ in a way that is acceptable. Alice’s action towards her cat describes her anxiety of the tidiness that she cannot manage because of her cat; as a result, she blames and tells it that it is her cat’s fault.

“When will Dinah have finished with your White Majesty, I wonder? That must be the reason you were so untidy in my dream – Dinah!” (Carroll, p.189). Again, she characterizes her cat as the untidy White Queen. It implicitly tells that Dinah is untidy undergoing its toilet and Alice does not like untidiness; nevertheless, she is an unorganized girl. Freud in Snowden (2017:113) stated that “The anal phase is the time when social conditioning really begins to come into play.” In the phase of psychological development, it is the phase of ‘anal’ when a child is forced to be tidy undergoing her toilet may develop into two typical behaviors: anal expulsiveness (disordered or antisocial) and anal retentiveness (neat and tidy). It indicates that Alice is experiencing hard training of toileting from her parent, resulting in her disordered behavior ‘expulsiveness.’ However, she denies this by blaming Dinah is untidy that is represented in White Majesty. Her defense mechanism of projection proceeds in this context in which she wishes to be well-organized in reality cannot be accepted; she believes that her cat Dinah is untidy. Furthermore, the White Queen can be symbolized as a parent; at this point, it is a mother as a source norm from whom a child’s ‘ego’ develops into ‘super-ego.’

Based on the description of the reality and the fantasy regarding her tidiness, it is concluded that she is having difficulty to manage her emotion. It is seen when she is often angry with her cat whenever something is untidy in reality. Erikson in Syed, McLean (2017:3) stated that “Toilet training as the beginnings of understanding the processes of “holding on and letting go,” which are fundamental to future development.” A child during this tension develops the sense of autonomy; either to be self-sufficient in many activities, including toileting, feeding, walking, exploring, and talking or the doubt of her own abilities. During this period, a child has very little control of the processes of holding on and letting go. Therefore, exercises of these activities need to be trained, followed by giving autonomy and praises. Erikson (1993:253) stated that “This stage, therefore, becomes decisive for the ratio of love and hate, cooperation and willfulness, freedom of self-expression and its suppression.” Limiting a child’s autonomy regarding this matter causes the feeling of anxiety resulting in pessimistic or helpless personality. She expresses her feelings and emotion to her cat as a defense mechanism of displacement. In addition, seeing her kitty have a problem of toilet training, she blames it to her as an object of her projection, indicating that she experiences a hard potty training from her mother that makes

her obsessed with tidiness. As a matter of fact, she is depicted as an unorganized girl who just loves tidiness in her fantasy. This obsession appears due to her wish to be like her mother, who loves tidiness as a role model.

'Well, you can be one of them then, and I'll be all the rest.' And once she had really frightened her old nurse by shouting suddenly in her ear, 'Nurse!' Do let's pretend that I'm a hungry hyena, and you're a bone!'" (Carroll, p.18).

Queen and king can be interpreted as the symbols of parents. Such play can be implied as her wish to be an adult person; that of parents are the source of morals and role models in a family where a person's 'ego' may develop into 'super-ego.' Here, she gives in the pretend to play by requesting her sister to choose her demand rather than to urge her in order to fulfill her wish. She even compellingly invites her nurse to play pretend as a hungry hyena and her nurse to be a bone. Hyena can be symbolized as the 'id' that demands the pleasure of fulfilling hunger by eating the bone. This can also be interpreted as Alice's dietary habit problem. In the previous analysis, she does not mind for not having many dinners, and in this context, hyena eats raw meat but not a bone. This is a piece of evidence that supports her dietary habit problem. The second problem is, a girl is supposed to be close to her parents other than a nurse. It indicates that she has a gap relationship with her parents. *"Look on the branch above your head," said the Gnat, "and there you'll find a Snap-dragon-fly. Its body is made of plum pudding, its wings of holly leaves, and its head is a raisin burning in brandy."* (Carroll, p.61). The described insect can be interpreted as the drive of her 'id'; the needs of a healthy diet in order to grow well. The wings of holly leaves are the sex symbol of a figure of a male; meanwhile, the plum pudding is the opposite. Therefore, the insect itself is also the representative of her parents' wish of wanting her to have a good eating habit. The sweets that the insect is made of represents the favorite unhealthy food that she usually consumes.

Based on the description of reality and the fantasy regarding her dietary habit, it is concluded that she is difficult to avoid consuming sugary food. Erikson (1993:256) stated that "The child indulges in fantasies of being a giant and a tiger, but in his dreams, he runs in terror for dear life." A child's fantasy of being a wild animal; a defense mechanism as an escape from anxiety, represents a fear of unwanted things that happen in reality. She tries to avoid having so much food; on the contrary, her fantasy depicts her favorite sweets, indicating that there is a restriction to having much food regarding dietary habit from her mother who wants her to have an ideal proportion of the body. Nevertheless, this is difficult to be done by Alice that makes her play pretend as a defense mechanism of sublimation to reduce her anxiety in her reality; meanwhile, her 'id' is gratified with objects of sweets in her fantasy. Erikson (1993:253) stated that "From the sense of self control without loss of self-esteem comes a lasting sense of good will and pride; from a sense of loss of self-control and of foreign over control comes a lasting propensity for doubt and shame." Giving a punishment to Alice's cat is a form of her unstable emotion. The loss of self-control which comes from her anxiety towards her own mistakes portrays her guilt of being untidy or her incompetence of making decisions or acting independently.

"She had had quite a long argument with her sister only the day before – all because Alice had begun with 'Let's pretend we're kings and queens...' (Carroll, p.16). She used to have a long argument about pretending to be kings and queens because there were only two of them. It implicitly tells that she does not have many friends to play with; moreover, she frequently has a conflict with her sister whenever she plays with her. In psychoanalysis context, the projection mechanism is occupied with diverting the conflict to a comfortable situation to gratify the demand of 'id.' In addition, another defense mechanism that is occupied is 'fantasy,' in order to make herself comfortable. Adams (2014:79) stated that "psychotic symptoms of schizophrenia; paranoid, delusional, and hallucinatory, as well as melancholic, or depressive." Having too much repression of this may result in a person to have a neurosis; delusion, a false belief about unrealistic things or even the worst thing; schizophrenia, the inability to distinguish between reality and fantasy.

"But certainly was funny," (Alice said afterward when she was telling her sister the history of all this) "to find myself singing 'Here we go round the mulberry bush.' I don't know when I began it, but somehow I felt as if I'd been singing it a long, long time!" (Carroll, p.71). This account has something to do with her sister when she quite often invites her sister to play pretend of kings and queens. Alice thinks that it is funny

that it cannot be done; meanwhile, her sister can be anything she wants, and Alice will be the rest. She remembers this like the way the nursery rhyme ringing in her head, somehow she does not know when it happens.

Based on the description of the reality and the fantasy regarding her relationship with her sister, it is concluded that she has a relationship which is not quite well with her sister. It is because they often have a misconception regarding the pretend to play in reality. In contrast, she has a wish to avoid conflict with her sister in her fantasy. It is indicated that her dream as a defense mechanism tries to reduce her anxiety of having a conflict with her sister. Her biggest wish is to be able to get a solution to her problem and get on well with her sister.

“‘*I was watching the boys getting in sticks for the bonfire – and it wants plenty of sticks, Kitty!*’” (Carroll, p.15). The boys’ action getting in sticks for the bonfire outside the window attracts her attention. In psychoanalysis, of what Freud believes; a stick is a symbol of the male genital organ. Freud in Snowden (2017: 65) stated that “Sticks, knives, umbrellas, trees, and other pointy or penetrating objects represent the penis.” This signifies that there is a repressed desire for her interest in a male figure. Afterward, she says that the bonfire wants plenty of sticks, indicating the representation of her unconscious wish to be able to get close to the figure of her desired opposite sex; at this point, she seeks a figure of a male that is similar to her father. In the stage of psychological development, there is a phase when a girl reduces her interest with her father and starts to have an interest in another boy instead. This occurs when a child gets more and more exposure of morals; it is when ‘ego’ develops into ‘super-ego.’

“‘*But the tune isn’t his own invention,*’ she said to herself. *‘It’s ‘I give thee all; I can no more.’*” (Carroll, p.148). The song is about how an aged man lives his own life whom she used to know, by selling mutton pie. In her dream, she relates the song of ‘*A-Sitting On A Gate*’ as well as the tune of ‘*I give thee all, I can no more*’ from which it tells an aged man that represents a figure of a father whom she must obey because as the head of a family, a father earns money for his family. Hence, as a parent, he is the source of the central moral for Alice.

Based on the description of the reality and the fantasy regarding her relationship with her father, it is concluded that there is a repressed wish of a figure of a father. In reality, it is seen when she sees the boys gathering sticks outside; it is interpreted as a repressed desire for her interest in a male figure. It is a representation of her unconscious wish to be able to get close to the figure of her desired opposite sex; at this point, she seeks a figure of a male that is similar to her father. On the other hand, in the context of the fantasy, she adores a figure of an aged man signifying a male figure in her family. In the context of Alice’s family, a father is the head of a family whom she must obey.

“‘*Oh! I do so wish I could see that bit! I want so much to know whether they’ve a fire in the winter: you never can tell, you know, unless or, fire smokes, and then smoke comes up in that room too*’” (Carroll, p.18). It implicitly tells that she wonders whether she can get the warmth of her life correlated with her family in her fantasy. Moreover, she adds unless the fire smokes, and it comes up in that room too; this means that she misses something in her home that she cannot make it real. On this account, the room symbolizes her home; meanwhile, the fire symbolizes the warmth related to family matter.

“*This time she came up upon a large flowerbed, with a border of daisies, and a willow tree, growing in the middle.*” (Carroll, p.35). There, she is offered with a good view, as far as she can see the flowerbed, with a border of daisies, and a willow tree, growing in the middle. It signifies that she feels comfortable enough at this time in her dream. The flowerbed symbolizes the female sex organ; meanwhile, the willow tree symbolizes the male sex organ and the border of daisies can be symbolized as the first start, harmony, and purity. This can be interpreted as her wish to have harmonious parents in marriage. If it follows the rule of the glass world that all goes the other way, it can be seen that in reality, there is a problem between Alice’s parents.

The picture shows the illustration of the eight squares where Alice should go when the Red Queen is telling her about it. The two characters are drawn small in the distance to show the full view of the scenery to the viewers. Hence, the characters are illustrated looking at the eight squares from far away, letting the viewers feel the hope of Alice regarding the journey she is going to go. In addition, the full view of scenery with

contrast colors helps create the viewers' image of the autumn season. Besides, the illustration of the characters with the view let the readers see the entire world that the author tries to convey in the story.

Figure 4. Looking at the Distance

“It’s a great huge game of chess that’s being played – all over the world – if this is the world at all, you know. Oh, what fun it is! How I wish I was one of them! I wouldn’t mind being a pawn, if only I might join – though of course, I should like to be a Queen, best.” (Carroll, p.46). A huge game of chess can be interpreted as the life of the relationship between Alice and her mother. In the interpretation of dreams, chess is symbolized as a female sex organ which signifies the figure of her mother. The game is the set of rules that Alice should follow from her mother. Alice has a problem with her potty training that implies that she cannot do like what her mother wants. In her very age, Alice is a child who really wants to get close to her mother as well as dreams to be like her mother. On the other hand, she needs to play with her peers either at school or neighborhood who requires the support of her parents and teachers. In fact, it does not happen in her reality.

Based on the description of the reality and the fantasy regarding kinship, it is concluded that she has a kinship that is not entirely harmonious and warm. It is seen in the reality that she often plays alone and tends to be close to her cat rather than her very close persons in her family. In addition, she has a repressed wish to have the warmth of a family that she used to have. Hence, she also needs support and guidance from her parents; however, this cannot be actualized. On the contrary, the fantasy depicts her wish to have a harmonious family. Thus, the fantasy sends her signal always to obey her parents. Besides, she also has a repressed wish of having her conflict solved in the fantasy.

“let’s pretend that you’re the Red Queen, Kitty! Do you know, I think if you sat up and folded your arms, you’d look exactly like her. Now do try, there’s a dear!’ And Alice got the Red Queen off the table, and set it up before the kitten as a model for it to imitate...” (Carroll, p.18). Alice insists her cat to imitate the Red Queen that is put before her cat. Logically, it is not possible for a cat to imitate a human, like what Alice wishes that her cat can sit up and fold her arms. Having discontent experience playing with her sister and her nurse, it implicitly tells that in order to reduce the anxiety of her ‘ego’ to satisfy the wish of ‘id’ because of having no one to play with, her ‘ego’ occupies defense mechanism by projecting the cat as a friend to play with. Therefore, she urges as if her cat could imitate a human-like figure of Red Queen.

“O Tiger-lily,” said Alice, addressing herself to one that was waving gracefully about in the wind, “I wish you could talk!” (Carroll, p.35). This Tiger-lily is a symbol of true friendship; when Alice wishes the lily could talk, it can be interpreted as her wish of a bond of friendship in reality. In fact, she is a lonely girl who loves to spend most of her time to talk to her cat and play with her own fantasy. At once, Tiger-lily replies to Alice that they can talk when nobody is worth talking to. It implies that all her wishes in fantasy can be fulfilled.

Based on the description of the reality and the fantasy regarding her loneliness, it is concluded that she is a lonely girl. In reality, she always invites her cat to play chess and pretend. Besides, she also characterizes her cats as humans whom she can talk to and understand what Alice instructs them to do. Meanwhile, in the fantasy, it is depicted as a symbol of flower that represents her repressed wish of having a strong bond of friendship with her peers.

Results and Discussion

Upon analyzing the data, the research being conducted was to figure out how Alice manages her 'id' towards the reality principle in *Alice through the looking glass* novel, how the fantasy in *Alice through the looking glass* novel works as defense mechanism and how the reality and the fantasy in *Alice through the looking glass* novel portray Alice's identity crisis. The result of the research identified the problem found, the issues, the identity crisis, and the personality of the character Alice.

The first problem found was the issue within the members of Alice's family. Alice is seen having a conflict with her sister in term of the misconception of pretend play of kings and queens. She requests her sister to be the queen; meanwhile, Alice herself to be the rest of the king, which is unacceptable in reality. At this point, her sister cannot accept her request because a king is a character who is played by a boy. Similarly, in her fantasy, she wishes to become a queen, representing the wish to be like her mother. In addition, it is found that Alice has a wish to reduce her anxiety when she tries to end the conflict between Tweedle Dum and Tweedle Dee. Thus, her dream is her defense mechanism to fulfill her wish to be able to get on well with her sister, which cannot be done in her reality.

The conflict with her mother is seen in her projection in reality when her cat makes the wool thread in a mess. She tries to punish her cat by not giving her dinner as a punishment; however, she takes the punishment for herself instead and does not want to be blamed for it. It is her denial as a defense mechanism when all this happens because of her own carelessness, and she denies it as if it were the kitten's fault. The other problem is seen when Alice wishes her kitten to be taught well for toilet manners by Dinah, the kitten's mother. It is also her defense mechanism of projection due to her wish to be like her mother, who concerns about tidiness; nevertheless, she is untidy or unorganized. In the fantasy, it is her wish to be able to do what her mother expects her like rules, tidiness, clean toileting, and healthy diet which she is unable to do them in her reality.

In the part of the looking-glass insect, it depicts Alice's unhealthy dietary habit, which is the love of sugary food. This issue has become her mother's concern which contradicts to her habit. As a result, her fantasy tries to send a signal to her ego to manage her eating habit like Alice wishes what her mother expects her to do. Similarly, it is seen in the reality when she does not mind having dinner as a punishment of what she considers it as the kitten's fault, letting the wool messy.

Another issue is seen when she also misses the warmth of her both parents. In reality, it is seen when she unintentionally sees the boys picking up sticks which symbolize the figure of the male parent. Besides, she wonders whether snow loves the trees and fields that the overall context is interpreted as the intense relationship between her and her parents. Similarly, in her fantasy, when she wishes to be able to get back to her house and her old room. It signifies that she has a hidden wish to get the warmth of her parents like she used to have.

In the Humpty Dumpty part, it illustrates all her wish regarding her parents' expectation towards Alice that she cannot actualize. It is pictured as a high wall which Alice cannot get through it. In the same part, Humpty Dumpty judges Alice like a child who can hardly do anything. Her mother's personality is depicted through this in which she only judges Alice without giving her support or motivation when she fails to do something. It can be seen that her mother is typical of a strict mother who sticks to rules.

In term of an identity crisis, Alice has been experiencing three stages of psychosocial development. Erikson (1993:248) stated that "The amount of trust derived from earliest infantile experience does not seem to depend on absolute quantities of food or demonstrations of love, but rather on the quality of the maternal relationship." In other words, the quality of maternal relationship between a child and a mother is the basic infantile trust which can develop to trusting people around her. At her seven and a half years of age, Alice is experiencing the phase of 'industry versus inferiority.' It is the time when a child busily learns to be competent and productive in mastering new skills, or feels inferior, unable to do anything well. It is seen that she becomes an inferior child who tries to divert her own problem with her projection to her cat and her fantasy as the result of repressed desires within herself towards her family. Hence, she often has a long argument with her sister during playtime. The factor of her withdrawal is caused by the judgment she feels from her parents. It causes her to be an unconfident child who plays mostly with her cat and imagination as a projection of defense mechanism. Besides, her denial of her incompetence of being tidy influences her behavior to be a disorganized kid and harsh to the objects she plays with. As a result, she makes her mother a figure whom she is obsessed

to be. Her withdrawal from her close persons and peers as well as her incompetence, is evidence of her inferiority.

The correlation with her past phase of 'autonomy versus shame and doubt' is regarding her potty training and eating habit. A child learns either to be self-sufficient in many activities, including toileting, feeding, walking, exploring, and talking or the doubt her own abilities. The hard potty training that her mother taught her makes her a child who loves tidiness; in fact, she is messy. The lack of praise from her parents regarding potty training makes her tell her cat the same thing. It becomes a piece of evidence that she used to have: hard potty training. This influences her behavior in controlling her emotions and competence. She gets mad with her cats when they are messy; in fact, what causes this happens is her incompetence of winding the wool thread, putting the wool thread around her cat's neck. Hence, her denial of being untidy makes her punish the kitten. Regarding the eating habit, she loves sweets or sugary food that is described in her fantasy. Thus, reducing her portion of dinner is caused by the rules and the expectation of her mother that wanting her to have healthy food.

It can be seen that Alice is experiencing many hallucinations or uncontrolled fantasy, delusion: a belief of being what she wishes to be, disorganized behavior: messy, uncontrolled emotion, mean to animals, social withdrawal: spending most of her time alone, and paranoia: being afraid of mistakes. Erikson (1993:249) stated that "Ultimately, children become neurotic not from frustrations, but from the lack or loss of societal meaning in these frustrations." It explains that social development emerges from the infantile and childhood stages which later on develop to social skills. This reveals the importance of social interaction with the family and the surrounding environment. Such conditions can be suppressed in the subconscious which ultimately leads to mental disorders or neurosis "Out of this view came the concept of the Bleuler in Veague B. Heather, et al. (2007:4) stated that "schizophrenogenic mother," or a mother who caused schizophrenia in her child through her style of parenting." The hard nurturing from Alice's parents influences her social development, which results in neurosis. In this case, the role of parents in parenting becomes vital in the child's growth and development. The expectations that are too high can harm the child's behavior. Unconsciously, all that will put inner pressure on the child. The child will become obsessed and often feel guilty when unable to meet the expectations of parents. In this case, Alice is looking for escape through her fantasy to reduce the pressure she experiences. This fantasy will cause hallucinations and delusions that if it is not controlled, which is the beginning of schizophrenia. Veague B. Heather et al. (2007:2) stated that "Some schizophrenics show symptoms such as withdrawal, apathy, hallucinations, or delusions. The sub-types include Paranoid, Disorganized, Catatonic, and Residual." In the case of Alice, the hallucinations experienced were when she wildly fantasizes about the mirror world where everything inside is reversed. The delusion is when Alice believes that she is not real and is part of her fantasy or false belief. As a result of this, Alice becomes an apathetic person and withdraws from the outside world. In addition, Alice also experiences paranoia towards eating habits applied by her parents and has problems with tidiness or disorganized behavior. Based on the analysis above, these characteristics are the symptoms of Childhood Onset Schizophrenic personality disorder. This personality disorder refers to a person who has split mind; in this case, difficulty in differentiating the fantasy towards reality.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis of the reality and the fantasy of Alice through the Looking-Glass, it is concluded that Alice's life has the issues of a family matter, eating habit, social withdrawal, and disorganized behavior. As the conclusion of the research:

1. Alice's 'ego' cannot manage her 'id' which is difficult to be gratified in reality that triggers Alice overreacts her defense mechanisms. Alice's family matter lies in the relationship with her family members, especially her mother. The rules and hard potty training that she has experienced make her become a kid who loves tidiness, that of, in fact, she is messy. Regardless of her parents' expectations towards Alice, she becomes a child who wishes to be a mother-like kid. A figure of a mother is her role model, mirroring her actions in reality which wanting everything tidy and have rules. Her inability to become what her parents expect her to be, resulting in her having much anxiety within herself which she projects it to her pet cats.

2. Alice's fantasy works as a defense mechanism which is caused by her unfulfilled wishes in reality. It is revealed that she has a conflict with her sister when she asks her for role play. Feeling so much anxiety, she invites her nurse and eventually her cats to play with. Playing a pretend to play with her cats is her way to overcome or reduce her anxiety in order to be able to grant her wish; she cannot make it. In the fantasy, the conflict with her sister is described in the Tweedle Dee and Tweedle Dum part. It is illustrated that Alice has a wish to end his conflict with her sister that she cannot manage. In relation to her opposite-sex parent; father, it is described when she watches the boys collecting sticks for a fire, symbolizing her wish to have the warmth of a figure of her father. Similarly, in the fantasy, it is mainly illustrated in the poem of 'A-sitting on a gate.' It is interpreted as her wish to be able to have a figure of a responsible father who is as the head of the family and as the one that she admires. Besides, her love of sweets or sugary food is also the factor she tries to reduce her portion of dinner.
3. Alice experiences identity crisis at the phase of autonomy versus doubt and shame as well as initiative versus guilt which influences her behaviors, resulting Childhood Onset schizophrenic (COS) personality disorder. Things that happen in her family cause Alice to become a child who loves to play with her own cats and imagination. In reality, her loneliness is portrayed when she does not have the passion of playtime with her peers and parents but her nurse instead. During playtime, Alice has a conflict with her sister that often makes a long argument with her. As a result of her unfulfilled wishes, she often experiences hallucination during her pre-conscious and resulting in unconscious fantasy in her dream as a defense mechanism to reduce her anxiety.

All in all, based on the interpretation of the analysis, it can be seen that Alice is experiencing many hallucinations or uncontrolled fantasy, delusion: a belief of being what she wishes to be, disorganized behavior: messy, uncontrolled emotion, mean to animals, social withdrawal: spending most of her time alone, and paranoia: being afraid of mistakes. Based on the above characteristics from the result, it is concluded that Alice is experiencing Childhood Onset Schizophrenic (COS) Personality Disorder: the inability of her 'ego' to manage her anxiety, resulting in her behavior in which Alice as an early teenager is having difficulty in distinguishing the difference between reality and fantasy.

References

- Adams, M. V. (2014). *For Love of the Imagination: Interdisciplinary Applications of Jungian Psychoanalysis*. New York: Brunner-Routledge.
- Adams, M. V. (2014). *The Fantasy Principle: Psychoanalysis of the Imagination*. New York: Brunner-Routledge.
- Barry, Peter. (1995). *Psychoanalytic Criticism. The Beginning Theory: An Introduction to Literary and Cultural Theory*. Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1995, 95-120.
- Carroll, L. (2005). *Alice Through the Looking-Glass: Illustrated by Robert Ingpen*. London: Templar Publishing, Ltd.
- Dawson, C. (2002). *Practical Research Methods: A User-Friendly Guide to Mastering Research*. London: How to Books, Ltd.
- Ekins, R. (2002). *Unconscious Mental Life and Reality*. New York: H. Karnac (Books), Ltd.
- Erikson, H. E. (1993). *Childhood and Society*. London: W.W. Norton & Co, Inc.
- Frankie & Wallen. (2005). *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education*. London: McGraw-Hill Publishing Ltd.
- Freud, S. (2005). *Psychopathology of Everyday Life*. New York: Nabu Press.
- Freud, S., Freud, A. (2008). *The Essential of Psycho-Analysis* (Vols. 1-24). (C. Yorke, Ed., & J. Strachey, Trans.) London, The United Kingdom: Vintage Publishing.
- Heather, M. Ward. (2015). *Love and Sex Addiction within Victorian Literature: A Psychoanalysis of Jane Eyre and Dracula*. Postgraduate Thesis: Marshall University. The U.S.A: West Virginia.
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research Methodology: Methods & Techniques*. New Delhi: New Age International, Ltd.
- Lennox, M. (2015). *Over 1,000 Dream Symbols and Their Universal Meanings*. New York: Llewellyn Worldwide Ltd.

-
- Oliner, M. M. (2012). *Psychic Reality in Context: Perspectives on Psychoanalysis, Personal History, and Trauma*. London: H. Karnac (Books), Ltd.
- Rose, J. (2011). *Mapping Psychic Reality: Triangulation, Communication, and Insight; Psychoanalytic Ideas*. London: Karnac Books, Ltd.
- Snowden, R. (2017). *Freud: The Key Ideas; From psychoanalysis and sex to dreams, the unconscious, and more*. London: John Murray Learning, Teach yourself.
- Snowden, R. (2017). *Jung: The Key Ideas; From Analytical Psychology and Dreams to the Collective Unconscious and More*. London: John Murray Learning, Teach yourself.
- Syed, McLean. (2017). *Erikson's Theory of Psychosocial Development*. New York: PsyArxiv Preprints.